

MULTIPURPOSE SOLUTION FOR CONTACT LENS FOR THE PREVENTION OF MICROBIAL KERATITIS

Rafwana Ibrahim*, Dr. Vipin K V, Flency Baby, Asima K T, Dr. Ann Rose Augusthy

Department of Pharmaceutics, College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Government Medical College Kannur, Kerala University of Health Science, Kerala, India.

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ABSTRACT

Contact lens use has become more prevalent around the world and the associated ocular difficulties include microbial keratitis, redness, conjunctivitis, polymicrobial keratitis, contact lens-related corneal ulcer, and dry eyes. The use of an efficient multipurpose contact lens solution exhibiting a cleaning, disinfecting, lubricating, deproteinizing, and wetting effect would reduce the complications addressed by the use of contact lenses. Most of the currently available marketed formulations contain first-generation and second-generation antimicrobial agents having various drawbacks of corneal staining, antimicrobial resistance, etc. Medicinal plants have been used as a traditional treatment for ocular diseases for thousands of years in many parts of the world. Hence the use of herbal ingredients in these formulations could be promoted as they are more compatible with the human body, and has fewer side effects. This review explains contact lens induced microbial keratitis, multipurpose contact lens solution for its treatment, and various herbal medicines that are used for ocular disease treatment.

Corresponding author

Rafwana Ibrahim

Department of Pharmaceutics,

College of Pharmaceutical Sciences,

Government Medical College, Kannur,

Kerala university of health science, Kerala, India.

rafwana.ibrahim@gmail.com

(91) 8129060228

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INTRODUCTION

Contact lens wear is becoming more and more prevalent around the globe for multiple reasons related mostly to refractive error correction, myopia, cosmetic, and other therapeutic uses. However, the use of contact lens possess a risk of developing complications like polymicrobial keratitis, contact lens-related corneal ulcer, *Acanthamoeba* keratitis, and dry eyes. Until the widespread introduction of contact lenses (1970's), microbial keratitis was predisposed to infection due to disrupted ocular surface defense mechanisms, trauma, existing ocular diseases, and poor hygiene[1]. During the past decade, contact lens wear has become a common predisposing factor for microbial keratitis due to the improper cleansing and disinfection of contact lenses [2]. As a result, the incidence rates of bacterial keratitis increased exponentially from 0.5 per 10,000 people to 13.3-20.9 per 10,000 annually for extended-wear soft contact lenses whereas the risk associated with the use of therapeutic contact lenses was even much higher reaching 52/10,000 per year. [3]

The presence of microorganisms on contact lenses leads to infiltrative keratitis, an inflammatory condition, and microbial keratitis, an eye infection that might ultimately lead to vision loss. The factors involved in the occurrence of infiltrative keratitis are not entirely understood; however, it is hypothesized that continuous wear, the presence of deposits, and bacteria and toxins adherent to the lens are important etiological factors. With concern to microbial keratitis, it is well established that poor hygiene and continuous wearing schedules are the risk factors. Microbial keratitis is a term that includes bacterial keratitis, fungal keratitis, and *Acanthamoeba* keratitis. The most common etiological agents isolated from contact lens associated microbial keratitis are *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus* spp. No sooner, the contact lenses are inserted into the eyes, the endogenous lipids, proteins, and glycoproteins rapidly accumulate on their surface, thus favoring the adhesion of commensal bacteria and biofilm formation. This leads to infections caused by the proliferation of indigenous flora or other opportunistic pathogens.

Current epidemiological data suggest that microbial keratitis cases may exceed 2 million per year worldwide. In the early to mid-1980s, concern for microbial keratitis associated with contact lenses began to develop [1]. Irrespective of the material type of lenses, it has been shown that the use of contact lenses was the primary factor for corneal infection. Microbial keratitis associated with poor contact lens hygiene could be prevented or controlled with fewer incidence rates with the effective use of an efficient multipurpose solution.

The multipurpose solution is an all-in-one care system that is used to clean, rinse, disinfect, and store contact lenses. An ideal multipurpose solution, therefore contains a disinfectant preservative, surfactant, sequestering agent, buffers, isotonic agent, viscosity imparting agent, wetting agent, lubricant, and a deproteinizer. The effective use of a multipurpose solution helps to control the microbial load and should reduce the incidences of keratitis.

Based on the literature reviews it was revealed that almost every conventional contact lens solution to date either had first-generation antimicrobial preservatives like chlorhexidine, benzalkonium chloride, chlorobutanol, thiomersal, methyl paraben, propyl paraben, benzyl alcohol as the principal ingredient or second-generation antimicrobial preservatives like polyhexamethylene-biguanide or poly quad. All multipurpose solutions with first-generation antimicrobial preservatives were associated with incidents of ocular toxicities and poor efficacy and hence are not preferred these days. Even with the incorporation of second-generation antimicrobial preservatives, not every limitation could be overcome as studies still shows ocular toxicities and contamination of contact lens remaining unresolved in 30-80% of cases despite being regularly bathed in multipurpose solution which was designed and claimed to provide several log reduction of bacteria. This concludes that existing multipurpose lens care solution systems may not be as efficient enough to kill bacteria that grow as biofilms. This calls for the formulation of a multipurpose solution with superior antimicrobial efficacy, safety, and patient compliance.

Most chemical disinfectants are reported to have some kind of adverse effect on human tissues and can also develop microbial resistance over prolonged use. This indeed has been a matter of concern while formulating a multipurpose solution. On the other hand, ethanopharmacologists had screened many promising natural compounds with comparable antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties as synthetic agents but with lesser adverse effects.

MICROBIAL KERATITIS

Keratitis is a major inflammatory disease caused to the cornea, which may be associated with various infectious microorganisms like amoeba, bacteria, viruses, and fungus and may also be caused by non-microbial factors like trauma, chemical exposure, ultraviolet exposure, etc. Keratitis is associated with intense pain and usually impaired eyesight, photophobia, red eye, and a gritty sensation.

Earlier before the introduction of contact lenses as an alternative to spectacles, the major risk factors that were associated included trauma and microbial growth during inflammation and infections. After the introduction of contact lenses in the 1970s, contact lens wears become one of the predisposing factors for microbial keratitis due to poor hygiene, extended wear, and contact lenses associated ocular inflammations. Among these, the extended wear of contact lens become the major risk factor for microbial keratitis. During contact lens wears the chances for the microbes to enter the eye from the wearer's lid margins, their fingers upon lens insertion (or removal), or via the contact lens, from the care solutions, or the storage case is high. As an additional source of contamination improper use of lenses and their disinfection/cleaning systems plays a major role. [4]

Another important factor is the impact of contact lens wear on tear fluid, which protects the corneal epithelial cells against *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*. The tear fluid act against the microorganisms by directly affecting them or by upregulation of the defensive capacity of the epithelial cells. A contact lens has the ability to alter tear biochemistry at the corneal surface when it comes too closer to the cornea or reduces the tear mixing between the pre and post-lens tear compartment during blinking. The changes caused to ocular surface biochemistry could lead to various consequences including loss of direct or indirect defenses against microbes. [5,6]

The pathogenesis of microbial keratitis especially *Acanthamoeba* keratitis includes the initial adhesion of the microorganism to the stroma epithelium which may be favored by trauma, corneal abrasion, etc. This is then followed by corneal epithelial desquamation and stromal invasion. The stromal invasion includes the penetration and dissolution of the underlying collagenous stroma and causes cytotoxic events. The final stage is neuritis, the clustering of the corneal neurons.[7] The major causative organisms include gram-positive as well as gram-negative bacteria, fungus, mold, etc ranging from *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Fusarium solani*, *Escherichia coli*, *Candida Albicans*, *Serratia Marcescens*, *Acanthamoeba*.[8]

CONTACT LENS

Contact lenses interact with the ocular surfaces through the tear film, the corneal epithelium, and the conjunctival epithelium. To maintain aerobic metabolism, corneal metabolism, and tear stability, contact lenses should allow sufficient airflow. Contact lenses can be classified as soft, rigid, and hybrid contact lenses based on their composition.[9]

Rigid contact lens

Rigid contact lenses were initially made of glasses, which were later substituted by poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), which had many limitations including corneal respiration, which increases the risk of undergoing ocular complications. The introduction of thermoplastics like poly (4-methyl-1-pentene) and cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB) which exhibited 20 times higher oxygen permeability than that of PMMA, lead to the replacement of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA). However, the lack of dimensional stability and low hydrophobicity made them unsuitable as contact lenses which lead to the development of rigid gas-permeable contact lenses.[9]

Soft contact lens

Hydrophilic contact lenses are synthesized by co-polymerization of (hydroxyethyl)methacrylate (HEMA) with ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA). Its hydrophilic nature is in contrast to the hydrophobic nature of poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) and a lesser extent to cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB). Its increased permeability to water, oxygen, and other constituents of tears having low molecular weight appears to offer metabolic advantages. Lenses of this type have high water levels at equilibrium ie. 40%. [9]

The ideal characteristics of contact lenses are as follows[10]

- It should be biologically inert.
- It should be non-selective in the absorption of metabolites and toxins.
- It should not take part in enzymatic activity.
- It should not exhibit strong molecular adhesive forces.
- It should not show excessive electrophoretic osmotic properties.
- It should have little friction effect between the surface of the material and the eye tissues.
- It should have a high gas permeability.
- It should be compatible with the surface eye tissue electrical charges without a change of properties.
- It should not change its properties within the normal biological range of pH.
- It should not excite an inflammatory or immune response

The differences between soft and hard contact lenses are given in the table below:[10]

Table no 1: Difference between hard and soft contact lens.

SL No:	Hard contact lens	Soft contact lens (Hydrophilic contact lens)
1	Dimensionally stable	Dimensionally unstable
2	Made up of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA)	Made up of (hydroxyethyl) methacrylate (HEMA)
3	Does not react with water	Swells in contact with water and swelling depend on various factors like medication, variation in tear flow, and changes in atmospheric conditions.
4	The eye cannot tolerate these for more than 3 hrs.	The eyes can tolerate these for more than 7 to 8 hrs.
5	Oxygen permeability is less due to the nature of the material	Oxygen permeability is more due to the texture nature of the construction material.
6	Exhibit strong molecular forces	Does not exhibit strong molecular forces
7	Not very compatible with the surface of the eye	Very compatible with the surface of the eye
8	There is friction between the surface of the material and the eye tissues	There is no or very little friction between the surface of the material and the eye tissues.
9	No problems of deposition (only merit)	Problems of deposition which may cause Giant papillary conjunctivitis (GPC) and keratitis can be solved by using a multifunctional solution, proper lens hygiene, and proper hygienic conditions

AN IDEAL LENS CARE REGIMEN [10,11]

The ideal lens care regimen for soft contact lenses are

1. It should remove all types of surface deposits like dirt, fats, tear deposits, protein and cosmetics.
2. It should remove micro-organisms and their spores like bacteria, fungi, and viruses and should provide maximum antimicrobial coverage.
3. It should provide isotonicity to the lenses as well as hydration so that lenses remain in their optimum shape.
4. It should be compatible with tears to provide maximum comfort.
5. It should not sensitize ocular tissue and should be free from all allergic syndromes.

NEED FOR MULTIPURPOSE SOLUTION FOR CONTACT LENS

Contact lens contamination is a significant public health concern and may lead to the development of microbial keratitis in contact lens wearers. Patients should be educated to clean and disinfect the lens cases daily, and the necessary precautions to avoid contaminations. These would reduce the number of diseases caused in accordance with pathogenic microbes. [12]

The subject of a contact lens solution (CLS) is a broad one embracing the knowledge of a large number of chemicals and plastics and their properties and interaction in clinical use. The practitioner is concerned with the mechanism of action, efficacy, toxicity, and use of drugs involved but the formulator is concerned with the antimicrobial activity of the basic drug, the interaction of the basic drugs and other pharmaceutical adjuvants with the plastic container, contact lens material, and their compatibilities, shelf-life, stabilities, surface activities, wetting, lubricating and cushioning activities.

During the early stages of the development of hydrophilic lenses, it was thought that the hydrophilic nature of the surface would obviate the need for most solutions since wetting agents were unnecessary for the same reason and it was thought that the cleaning would also be unnecessary. However, as experience has been gained over the last few years the complexities of dealing with new materials for use in contact with the eye have become increasingly apparent. Further, while a large majority of hydrophobic lenses are still made from a single material (PMMA), hydrophilic lenses are made from many materials including different additives and widely varying physical and physiological properties. Perhaps the most difficult problem that has arisen with hydrophilic lenses is that of sterilization. Fortunately, a considerable number of conjunctival sacs do not contain pathogenic bacteria.[10,13]

In addition to the physical and chemical factors inhibiting pathogens, non-pathogens also contribute to the protection of the eye by competing with pathogens for nutrients. These factors combine to provide a relatively stable protective system for the eye against infection but this protective mechanism of the eye is disturbed in kerato conjunctivitis sicca due to insufficient or inadequate tears. Contact lenses unfortunately interfere with the eye's defense mechanisms. Hydrophilic lenses in particular prevent the lids from sweeping the cornea and interface with the tears washing the cornea. They probably raise the corneal temperature and can also induce breaks in the corneal epithelium. In reports that appear in the literature on corneal infection, contact lens wearers suffer from bacterial contamination which may be due to lens contamination or the use of contaminated solutions. If the contact lens is new then it is very difficult for bacteria to enter it but if it is old with ridges the bacteria can easily penetrate and spoil the lens. The tears liquid absorbed by lenses serves as an excellent bacterial culture medium. Further, due to surface irregularities in the lens occurring during manufacture, the eye secretions that adhere to the lens surface may permit a nidus to form where bacteria can aggregate and possibly be protected from the disinfection process. [4,5,10]

Many researchers have shown the penetration effect of *Aspergillus fumigatus*, and *Trichothecium roseum* (mold found in tap water) into the polymeric network of hydrophilic contact lenses. The mechanism of penetration is probably using enzymes present in micro-organisms that cause degradation of the lens material and permit entry for them [14]. Even though there is no apparent damage to the lens there is always a possibility that endotoxins synthesized by the fungus are bound within the plastic and hence disinfectants may not remove the toxins, bacteria, or fungi. Therefore the solutions used for cleaning and soaking contact lenses should be changed daily. Thus apart from antibacterial activity, soft lens disinfection must also have a fungicidal capability. A further problem occurring with hydrophilic lenses is that of deposits adhering to the lens surface. The main sources of these deposits are ocular secretions, tap water contaminants that may have been adsorbed by the lenses, eye drops, finger dirt, eye makeup, and contaminants introduced during manufacture and from the atmosphere. The bulk of deposits, however, are mucoproteins from the tear liquid. Also found are calcium, iron, and other insoluble divalent and trivalent metal salts if impure water for storage or rinsing solutions has been used. Environmental and occupational factors also affect the cleanliness of lenses. Some eye drops containing phenylephrine, adrenaline, or berberine cause discoloration, and some preservatives from sterilizing and hydrating solutions may concentrate in the matrix of soft lenses causing either discoloration or surface filming and consequently discomfort to the lenses [15]. The use of cosmetics such as lipstick, mascara, oily creams, and shampoos may also contaminate the lens. This may cause symptoms of discomfort, lowered acuity, lens discoloration, and conjunctival infection. For these reasons, the development has taken place for daily cleaning solutions to prevent surface deposits from building up and rejuvenating products to remove deposits already present on the lenses.

The gradual build-up of deposits on the lenses requires a more effective cleaning treatment at periodic intervals depending on the patient, lens material, method of disinfection, etc. Although hydrophilic lenses offer many advantages over hard contact lenses, still some discomfort is experienced or a temporary drop in vision occurs while the lenses are worn. The main disadvantage of a hydrophilic contact lens is the deposition due to the construction of the material being used [10]. All these point to the need for an all-in-one system for cleansing, lubricating, deproteinizing, and wetting the contact lens to increase the safety of its use.

SOFT CONTACT LENS CARE REGIMEN USING DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS

The usual sequence of events followed conventionally before the development of multipurpose solutions during soft lens wear and care initially:-

1. Cleaning of the contact lenses after removal from the eye
2. Rinsing with a suitable saline rinsing solution.
3. Disinfecting using another solution containing the antimicrobial substance.
4. Deproteinizing gently so that no sensitization reactions occur and for this purpose, an enzyme tablet is used.
5. Lubricate with the lubricating solution.
6. Soaking in preserved saline solution.

MULTIPURPOSE SOLUTION FOR HYDROPHILIC CONTACT LENS

Multipurpose contact solutions are generally intended to combine the actions of cleaning, storing, wetting, and rinsing in one single lens care product. The rationale behind the manufacture of such a solution is to avoid confusion about the multiplicity and overall expenses of conventional lens care solutions. Most contact lens practitioners came across patients who omit one or more steps of the hygiene regimen in using conventional lens care solutions simply because they run out of the appropriate solution. The basic components of combination cleaning and storage solutions are similar to the individual solution with these functions. The combination of different lens hygiene functions into a multifunctional solution has elicited a possibility of the compromise of efficacy in these products. The very basic idea of formulating a multipurpose solution is to formulate a single-step solution for contact lens wearers due to the non-acceptance and non-compliance of the traditional 5-6 steps solution by the wearer. Although contact lenses were introduced in the 1970s, their popularity was limited to a special class of people. This was mainly due to its old technology and high cost and the very difficult six steps of the maintenance regimen i.e. cleaning, disinfecting, rinsing, soaking, lubricating, wetting, and deproteinizing.[16]

The contact lens wearer previously had to carry out the six different steps using six different solutions and it was a cumbersome exercise and omission of even a single step could have led to serious consequences that included giant papillary conjunctivitis, microbial keratitis, corneal ulcer, inflammation of the eye, lagophthalmos, insensitive cornea, neuroparalytic keratitis, scarring of cornea/perforations and even permanent loss of vision. Out of hard contact lens, semi-soft contact lens, soft contact lens, and disposable contact lens, soft contact lenses plays an important role and are being used widely. Despite several advantages and the immense popularity of hydrophilic contact lenses, these require far more care than their hard counterpart. This is due to the very basic nature of the material of construction which allows penetration of contaminants deep into the lens matrix. This sorption of contaminants leads to the deposition of various unwanted components that leads to many complications. Soft contact lenses suffer from several disadvantages of surface deposits that tend to build up on their surface mainly dirt, lipids, proteins, mucin, pigments, calcium salts, iron, mercury salts, chemical preservatives, and microbial contamination that includes bacteria, fungi, yeast, and protozoa. These deposits result in a variety of problems mentioned earlier which may ultimately cause loss of vision. Disfigurement of soft contact lenses may take place like changes in curvature and diameter changes if storage conditions are not maintained. [17,18]

An ideal multipurpose solution should contain the following properties[13]

- Remove all types of surface deposits like dirt, fat, tear, protein, cosmetics, and chemicals.
- Provide maximum anti-microbial coverage against bacteria, fungi, yeast, virus, and protozoa.
- Provide hydration, and iso-tonicity to the lenses and keep them in an optimum shape.
- Compatible with tears to provide maximum comfort.
- It should not sensitize eye tissues and should be free from all allergy syndromes.
- Non-toxic to ocular tissues.
- Compatible with all contact lens materials.
- Simple to use.
- Rapid disinfection capability.
- Condition lens surface to enhance wettability and eye comfort.
- Minimise deposition of tear film components.
- Inexpensive to purchase.

Functions of multipurpose solutions[13]

The functions of multipurpose contact lens solution is given in table no 2.

Table no 2: Diverse functions of multipurpose contact lens solution.

Criteria	Function
1. Cleaning	To remove dirt, lipids, fats, cosmetics, and pollutants.
2. Disinfecting	To provide an anti-microbial coating.
3. Rinsing solution	Rinse the lens after cleaning.
4. Soaking solution	To restore hydration and antimicrobial treatment and overnight storage.
5. Lubricating solution	To lubricate and rewet the lens during wear.
6. Deproteinizing	To remove protein deposits.

COMPOSITION OF MULTIPURPOSE SOLUTION[13,19,20]

All six steps if earned out by different solutions in the conventional cleaning regimen one by one, then omitting even a single step can lead to serious consequences which may ultimately lead to loss of vision. Hence there is a need for a single formulation that should fulfil all the diverse criteria. The multipurpose solution should have the following composition:-

1. Basic drug

Preservatives and antimicrobial agents are considered the basic ingredient of multipurpose contact lens solutions. Preservatives used in contact lens solution need to be effective against common gram-negative bacteria, gram-positive bacteria, fungi, and yeast, without being toxic to the eye and interfering with the basic chemical action of the solution used. Preservatives used should be broad spectrum, nontoxic, rapidly acting, non-allergic, non-sensitizing, non-irritating, and compatible (chemically and pharmacologically) with the other ingredients. Contact lenses should not alter the pH and tonicity of the solution.

2. Chelating agent

The chelating agent should be capable of inactivating metals in a solution and enhancing the effectiveness of the other agents. It should also prevent discoloration due to trace metals, and prevent oxidation catalyzed by trace metals. EDTA is considered to be an effective chelating agent.

3. Cushioning Agent

These compounds are used as thickeners, protective colloids, binders, stabilizers, and suspending agents. Their primary purpose is to cushion the lens against the eye. Cushioning agents act by lubricating the lens and by providing the surface of the lens with the mechanical buffer for a short time after insertion of the contact lens into the eye. Through this action, they also prevent contamination from fingers. Cushioning agents are also good wetting agents because they increase the contact time of drugs on the surface of the eye. Examples of cushioning agents are methyl cellulose, polyvinyl pyrrolidone, polyvinyl alcohol, and octaxynol.

4. Surfactant/cleaner

One of the most important aspects of any lens care regimen is the use of a prophylactic cleaning step in the normal daily hygiene routine to remove mucus, dirt, cosmetics, and other environmental contaminants. From a microbiological point of view, a clean lens is far easier to disinfect than a dirty lens as the removed contaminants cannot inactivate the preservative. Furthermore, these deposits can build up in due course of time and are sufficient to interfere with vision, lens wettability, and wearing comfort unless adequate prophylactic cleaning is carried out daily. For formulating and developing a multipurpose solution for contact lenses, a non-toxic, non-ionic cleaning agent has to be used for providing cleaning, rinsing, soaking, disinfecting, and deproteinizing action. The cleaning agent selected should not be a detergent type as it should not be harsh to the contact lenses as well as should not damage the cornea. Surfactants used can be polysorbates, poloxamers, triton, tyloxapol, pluronics, and polaxamine.

5. Isotonic and Buffering Agents

Sodium, potassium, and chloride may be added to make the solution isotonic with tears. However, the importance of isotonicity has been overemphasized in the past, especially for the small quantities involved on a contact lens and a range of 0.7-1.2% sodium chloride equivalent is acceptable and is the normal range of tears.

6. Deproteinizing Agents[21]

Since most deposits on the lens are primarily protein deposits it seems logical that enzyme cleansers would be effective. Enzyme cleaners do not damage the lens and are non-toxic and are fairly specific for lens deposits but they may have the potential for sensitizing the eye. The protein bath may develop an odor after a few hours of use and enzyme preparations may produce discoloration of the lens. The enzymes available are - purified papain, pancreatin, and trypsin. The non-enzymatic protein cleansers are citrate, hydranate, and tris buffer. Ideally, contact lenses should provide clear vision at all times, be completely comfortable and safe for extended wearing periods, not interfere with corneal metabolism, not cause ocular disease, and be long-lasting, easy to use, and economical. Unfortunately, such contact lens does not exist. One reason is that pre corneal tear film layer of the human eye contains organic substances such as lipids, proteins, pigments, bacteria, viruses, environmental contaminants, and inorganic substances, all of which interact with each other and the contact lens material to form a complex biofilm layer which binds to the contact lens material within minutes of placing the lens on the eye. This biofilm layer increases in thickness with each successive wearing period, eventually causing blurred vision, ocular discomfort, allergic eye diseases, or potentially serious ocular infections. Non-enzymatic protein cleansers are preferred because they are non-allergic and beneficial compared to enzymatic cleansers.

The basic functions of deproteinizing agents are given below:-

- Loosen ionically bound protein deposits from each other and the lens surface.
- Permits the mechanical removal of loosened protein deposits by friction rubbing.
- Pancreatin/citrates assist in removing mucoid and lipid deposits.
- Maintains good vision and comfort.
- Extends the useful life of all lenses.

HERBAL ACTIVE INGREDIENT FOR THE OCULAR DISEASES

In developing and developed countries during the past decade, there has been an increase in the interest and acceptance of natural therapies. The lower side effects, toxicity, cost, and higher safety compared to synthetic drugs makes a higher demand for herbal medicines. Herbal medicine is important in primary health care for about 75-80% of the world's population, especially in developing countries, because it is more culturally accepted, more compatible with the human body, and has fewer side effects [22]. In developed countries such as Germany, France, European Union, and the United States, its use has increased significantly in recent years. [22,23]

Today a significant part of the population is being affected by ophthalmic conditions, and most of them could be treated with antibiotics and steroids. However, the prolonged use of these could be may lead to toxicity and resistance. Due to the problems of resistance and adverse effects, there is much ambiguity regarding the use of antibiotics. Also, they are costly and beyond the reach of poor patients which could be solved to an extent by the use of herbal medicines. The longstanding history of the traditional use of herbal medicines is the common argument that favors its use. Even after being used from ancient times, plant-derived medicines can results in some adverse reactions so the need has been raised for safety evaluation [24]. Microorganisms develop resistance to present-day antibiotics that have created an immense clinical problem in the treatment of infectious diseases. Medicinal plants have been used to cure many ailments based on the experience of many physicians and the traditional systems of medicine that is of different ethnic societies. The use of medicinal plants in modern medicine suffers only from the fact that scientific evidence in terms of modern medicine is lacking in most cases. However, scientific proof to justify the use of a plant or its active principles is one of the important necessities today. It is still a problem to use these medicinal plants for ophthalmic problems. The practice of using herbal drugs in the treatment of eye ailments is well documented in Unani and Ayurvedic literature.[23,24]

Table no 3: Herbal plants for ocular diseases.

Sl No:	Herbal plant	Part of plant	Review
1.	Abelmoschus esculentus[25]	Fruit, flower	The flower and the fruit exhibited antifungal activity and could be used for the treatment of conjunctivitis and other fungal infections of the eye.
2.	Acacia Arabica, Acacia macracantha [26,27]	Bark	The bark extract mixed with honey is used in the eye to relieve conjunctivitis.
3.	Allium sativum [28]	Bulb	Sensitive against microorganisms including bacteria, fungi, protozoa, and viruses. Pseudomonas aeruginosa biofilms on soft contact lenses are inhibited and removed. A. sativum alcoholic extracts have the potential in inhibition of biofilm formation of S.pneumoniae, P. aeruginosa, and K. pneumonia more than their ability to destroy the biofilm of these bacteria.
4.	Aloe vera[29]	Fleshy leaf	The medicinal activity of Aloe vera compounds against eye disorders is considered within two groups of actions: antioxidant reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavenging and production of nitric oxide (NO)] and immunomodulatory (influence on mainly proinflammatory or anti-inflammatory cytokine level).
5.	Argemone Mexicana[30]	Latex	Latex is used for the treatment of ophthalmic infections.

6.	Radix scutellariae [31]	Dried root	The lack of cytotoxicity of R. scutellariae and C. phellodendri extracts suggests that these are potentially suitable for use in ocular preparations with potential use in the prevention and treatment of ocular infections, including Acanthamoeba keratitis.
7.	Camellia sinensis, Commelina erecta [30]	Inflorescences	Drops of the liquid from the floral spathes are used for the infected eyes.
8.	Cannabis sativa[32]	Leaf (Cannabinol)	Cannabinol oil extracted from Cannabis sativa metabolite was assessed for its activity in the inhibition and removal of P. aeruginosa biofilms on soft contact lenses.
9.	Cassia absus [33]	Leaf	The extract is used as an eye drop.
10.	Cinnamomum camphora, Cinnamomum zylanicum [24]	Crystals, Bark	The extract possesses antibacterial activity against gram-positive and gram-negative organisms.
11.	Commelina benghalensis [33]	Leaf	The extract is used as an eye drop.
12.	Cordia sinensis [34]	Leaf	The grounded rough leaves were used for the treatment of trachoma.
13.	Curcuma longa [24]	Rhizome (Curcumin)	Extracts exhibited anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties.
14.	Emblica officinalis [24]	fruit	Exudate obtained from the incisions of Emblica officinalis fruits is used as an external application for ocular inflammation. An aqueous was found to be a potent inhibitor of lipid peroxide formation and a scavenger of hydroxyl and superoxide radicals in vitro.
15.	Epidendrum sp [27]	Leaf, flower	Aqueous infusions are used for ophthalmic purposes.
16.	Euphorbia hirta [33]	Leaf	Used as an eye drop for the treatment of eye infection.
17.	Foeniculum vulgare [27]	Leaf, flower	Used in the treatment of conjunctivitis.
18.	Fumaria officinalis [35]	Leaf, stem. Flower	Traditionally used to cure eye infections.
19.	Heliotropium indicum[36]	Leaf, root	The juice obtained from the crushed plant part is used for the treatment of conjunctivitis.
20.	Iris germanica [27]	flower	Effectively used for ophthalmic purposes.
21.	Kalanchoe densiflora [34]	Leaf	Effectively used for ophthalmic purposes.
22.	Melospirum [24]	Honey	Recommended for sore eyes. It is also reported to prevent infection and promote healing, as it has ingredients similar to antibiotics.
23.	Mimosa pudica [37]	Leaf	Antimicrobial activities of the M. pudica against clinically important pathogens namely E.coli, S.aureus, B.subtilis, and S.typhi.
24.	Neem [38]	Leaf	Antibacterial activity against Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus pyogenes, Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, and Salmonella typhimurium.
25.	Ocimum sanctum [24]	Leaf (Eugenol)	Volatile and fixed oils are known for their anti-inflammatory activity. The essential oil possesses bactericidal activity against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria
26.	Pedelum murex [39]	Seed	Effective against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria and biofilm inhibitors.
27.	Pelargonium graveolens [27]	Flower	Rinsing the affected parts of the eye with the decoction of the flower is beneficial for the treatment of conjunctivitis
28.	Rhizome coptidis, Cortex phellodendri [40]	Rhizome (Berberine)	Berberine hydrochloride is effective for the treatment of eye conjunctivitis, and suppurative otitis media induced by Shigella dysenteriae, Escherichia coli, and Staphylococcus aureus.
29.	Ricinus communis [36]	Leaf	The leaf extract is used for the treatment of various eye infections including conjunctivitis
30.	Rosa centifolia [27]	Flower	Bathe the affected area by using a decoction of flowers. It helps in the treatment of conjunctivitis
31.	Rosa damascene [24]	Petals	Rose water obtained from petals have a soothing effect and is also found to be beneficial in ophthalmic treatment.
32.	Rostellularia crinata [33]	Leaf, flower, whole plant.	Juice is used for the treatment of eye infections.
33.	Spondias tuberosa [30]	Stem-bark	A decoction of a cup in a litre of water is used as a wash for the infected eyes
34.	Syzygium aromaticum [38]	Flower bud	Antibacterial activity against Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus pyogenes, Escherichia coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae, and Salmonella typhimurium.
35.	Terminalia chebula [24,41]	Seed powder, fruit	Antibacterial, antifungal, and antioxidant activity are useful for the treatment of ocular conditions.
36.	Zingibere officianalis [33]	Rhizome	Used as a remedy for the opacity of the cornea.
37.	Ziziphusg labrata [33]	Leaf	Macerated with water, filtered and the extract is used as eye drops
38.	Ziziphus oenoplia [33]	Leaf	The extract is used as an eye drop.

CONCLUSION

Microbial keratitis is a corneal inflammation mostly caused by the unhygienic use of contact lenses. These could be controlled to an extent by the use of an efficient multipurpose contact lens solution. Traditional medicines are extensively used from the past for various ocular diseases. Replacement of the conventional synthetic drug that causes resistance and other adverse effects with herbal ingredients with low cost and fewer side effects will be more beneficial.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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